

Creating Extruded FDM Composite Filament by Syringe Pumping of Nano-fillers

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Background

The properties of polymer composites are in part limited due to the powder coating method used to create them. Powder coating influences agglomerate formation, particularly for powders of differing size. Nanocomposites are particularly difficult to make, as nanoparticles inevitably segregate in the powder mixture. In this project, dispersed nano-fillers were syringe pumped directly into the melted polymer during extrusion to minimize agglomerate formation. The composite was then drawn out as 1.75mm 3D printer filament. Edge functionalized graphene (EFG) and laponite nano-particles were added to PLA, HDPE, and LDPE to create composites of up to 15wt%.

Syringe Pumping Nano-fillers

Syringe pumping is the controlled dripping of dispersed nano-fillers into the polymer matrix during extrusion. The solvent evaporates as the filler is pulled into the polymer. EFG and laponite were dispersed in water at 30mg/mL and 100mg/mL respectively.

Compound melt extrusion of FDM composite 1.75mm filament

Compared to a typical batch style powder coating production method, composite production by pumping:

- Minimizes nano-filler restacking, which in turn **lowers the agglomerate size**;
- Continuously extrudes composites without stalling production, leading to a **faster and cheaper** process
- **Minimizes nano-powder segregation and losses** to air
- **Agitation will benefit dispersion** rather than lead to segregation as it does during the controlled addition of powder mixed material to an extruder

Powder Mixing Process

Segregation of different sized powders

Morphology

Agglomerates in syringe pumped composites were **smaller**, had a **higher aspect ratio**, and were highly aligned with direction of extrusion.

Thermal Properties

Water caused no negative effect on onset degradation or the d1/2 temperatures. The hydrophilic laponite gel did not retain water in the polymer.

3D Printing

Electro-osmotic pumps were printed with PLA/EFG. HDPE printed composites successfully. Flow problems were experienced with LDPE.

Further Development

Syringe pumping has been shown to be an effective method of developing polymer nanocomposites, with potential to reduce agglomerate size and segregation without compromising thermal properties.

A greater composite filler wt% and improved dispersion could be achieved by injecting filler into the extruder under high pressure, with an exhaust hole close by for solvent evaporation..

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